

BASED ON THE DEFINITION OF CIVIL ADVANTAGES OF INDIVIDUALS: QUESTIONS OF THEORY AND PRACTICE

Leyla Mariusovna Burkhanova¹

¹ Candidate of Law, Associate Professor of the Department of "Private and Legal Disciplines" of a Specialized branch of Tashkent State Legal University

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ABSTRACT

In the context of the work carried out on a project of a new edition of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the theoretical aspects of the foundations of determining the legal capacity of individuals on the basis of current civil law standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan are considered. The relevance and scientific novelty of legal regulation of civil advantages of individuals are identified. The situation is justified that the idea of civil legal personality is associated with the presence of such qualities as legal capacity and capacity. It is determined that although civil rights belong to the person regardless of its legal capacity, but at the same time, only persons with legal capacity can be parties to individual civil legal relations. The provision is considered that although the law does not directly indicate the cessation of the legal capacity of the citizen declared dead, but the legislation did not "recognize the citizen who deceased", and "the declaration of him deceased", which emphasizes the difference between the establishment of the fact of death and the declaration of deceased, which is not Eliminates the possibility of the appearance of this person. It is considered that the legal capacity of an individual is a prerequisite for the prevalence of specific subjective rights, as well as equality in the ability to be a carrier of civil rights and obligations does not mean equality in specific subjective rights.

I. Introduction

The overwhelming major civil legal relationship occurs when physical persons participate. This aspect was taken into account when working on a draft new edition of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, since the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which carries out economic reforms to a new, higher level, is updated and improved. Updating civil law of the Republic of Uzbekistan is aimed at

continuing to modernize and liberalize the country, democratic updating of the political, legal and economic system, reliable protection of the rights and interests of the individual. Aside with these transformations, the issues of the legal status of individuals as subjects of civil law, which carry out their activities in all spheres of life, and have certain legal status - legal capacity and legal capacity.

Among the laws, the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan has special significance [1], the norms of which regulate property and personal non-property relations, determine the basic rights and obligations of civil law. Moreover, the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1] is the main for all national legislation in the field of entrepreneurship and the protection of citizens' rights. The Civil Code is a law of direct action and is applied every day in the practical activity of legal entities and individuals. In the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, head 3 "Citizens (individuals) of the subsection of 2" persons "are devoted to legal regulation of the legal capacity and capacity-capacity of individuals, in which the use of two terms" citizens "and" individuals "is enshrined, unlike previously operating GC of the Uzbek SSR 1963 [2], in which only the concept of "citizens" was present. Although the differences in the concepts of "citizen" and "individual" are well known, however, in the GC of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Citizens" and "individuals" are identical concepts, which is associated with the desire of the legislator to preserve the traditional and usual consumption of the term "citizen".

Citizens and the state are mutually connected with each other mutual rights and mutual responsibility. Citizens cannot be deprived or limited in rights and freedoms without a court decision. At the same time, the realization by citizens of their rights and freedoms should not contradict the legitimate interests of other citizens, states and society [3].

The concept of legal personality used in the modern theory of law determines what qualities the subjects of law should be possessed in order to have the right and

carry duties in the relevant branch of law. The idea of civil legal personality is associated with the presence of such qualities as legal capacity and legal capacity. Property relations regulated by civil law are accompanied by a person throughout his life: from the moment of birth and before his death. To properly regulate the economic turnover, it is necessary to give relations a sustainable nature in order to be attended by the conscious volitional action of the parties. But, and this confirms the practice, from the relations that are governed by civil law, cannot completely turn off citizens in whom, due to various reasons, there is no proper level of mental development. To solve such tasks in civil law, such categories as legal capacity and capacity appeared. The concept of "legal capacity" means the ability to have civil rights and carry duties, and the concept of "legal capacity" means the ability to acquire and exercise civil rights, to create civil duties and fulfill them. In accordance with the norms of civil law, legal capacity is recognized equally for all citizens from the moment of birth to death, and legal capacity arises from the moment of achieving a certain age, and in full - from eighteen years old, that is, the age of majority.

Considering the legal status of an individual (citizen), that is, its legal capacity and capacity, as a subject of civil law in the context of transformations in economic, political, social life, in particular, forming a class of owners, determine the relevance of this scientific article.

The purpose of the study is to consider the peculiarities of the right-hand capacity of the legal capacity of an individual in civil law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, its

grounds, features and formulation of some proposals for the improvement of this institution.

The scientific novelty of the study is determined by the fact that an attempt has been made to conduct a comprehensive study of issues related to the concept and foundation of the definition of an individual based on the norms of civil law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, some aspects of improving this institution have been identified.

II. Research methodology

The study was carried out on the basis of general scientific methods of cognition, as well as privately scientific research methods - logical, systemic, comparative law.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

In the works of the lawyers-civilists devoted to the legal regulation of the legal capacity and the capacity of individuals on civil law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a certain scientific analysis contains a certain scientific analysis. So, you can stay in some works of lawyers, such as Karkajaeva D.M. [4,5,6,], Egamemberdiev E.H [7,8,], Burkhanova L.M. [9,10,11,12,13], and others, in which the main issues relating to the legal status of individuals are considered. But theoretical and practical aspects of the study of legal regulation of the legal capacity and the capacity of individuals associated with changes in legislation have not yet been comprehensive scientific research.

Some aspects of legal regulation of the legal capacity and capacity-capacity of individuals are devoted to the study of such scientists of the theoreticals of the CIS countries, like Sergejev A.P., Tolstoy Yu.K. [14], Sukhanov E.V. [15], Weather L.R. [16] And others who are generally theory.

The same certain provisions of the Codex of the Republic of Uzbekistan on administrative responsibility [17], the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan [18], the Civil Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan [19], the Family Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan [20], the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan are devoted to the legal capacity of the legal capacity and capacity-capacity of individuals. Uzbekistan [21].

IV. Discussion and analysis

In accordance with Article 17 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, under legal capacity, it is understood as the ability to have civil rights and obligations, legal capacity is recognized for all citizens equally. The legal capacity of a citizen arises at the time of his birth and stops only his death [1]. However, in conceit to the death of the inheritant, at least not born by the opening of the inheritance, the right to inheritance arises, based on the proposal that they will appear, since the citizen is recognized only from the moment of its birth. Therefore, in the case of the birth of a living child, that is, the implementation of the specified proposal, its legal capacity, although it arises from the moment of birth, but in the field of hereditary offenses in the form of an exception is considered already at the time of the death of the inheritator. If the child was born alive, but died after his birth, only the testimony of his death is issued. From this we can conclude that in this case the legal capacity does not occur, but it is not. Indeed, in this case, only death certificate is issued, but the registry authorities, even if death has come in a few minutes, make up two records: about birth and death. Decisions of the issue was recognized whether the child born with the subject of law was

recognized and the possibility of inheritance on the right of submission depends on legal capacity.

According to another point of view, in conceit children, the right to inheritance is not recognized. In the interests of the child, assuming that he was born alive, only measures are taken to preserve his share inheritance. In justification of this position, it is indicated that only parents of the child and other legal representatives can require such a separation. However, after the birth of a child, until they achieve 14 years of minor, no requirements cannot present any requirements. Therefore, the above argument does not refute and the nominated position on the occupant, but not yet born child's right to inheritance.

Based on this, measures are taken to protect the possible rights of the future heir to the case of birth to his alive. Civil legal capacity provides the possibility of concrete subjective civil rights, their continuity, regardless of age, mental status for all citizens. Really civil rights, as a rule, can affliency to face regardless of its legal capacity, which depends on age and mental state. At the same time, it is necessary to keep in mind that only persons with legal capacity can be parties to individual civil legal relations. So only fully capable citizens are entitled to be representatives of trusted, guarantors, etc. In the form of an exception, partially capable citizens who have reached the labor majority can act as representatives of the organization when performing relevant duties by virtue of the employment contract (contract). Only a person who has at least partial capacity can be responsible for harmfulness, therefore, the volume of the legal capacity of individual citizens is not always equal and depends on their capacity. The restriction

allowed by law also make unequal capacity of individuals [16]. In addition, when it comes to citizens, the concept of civic legal capacity does not include the possibility of the right of civil rights that can arise only from organizations.

The legal capacity of the citizen is terminated at the time of his death [1]. Although the announcement of a citizen who deceased in its legal consequences is largely equal to the natural death of a citizen, such an announcement, if it is in reality, is alive, does not relieve its legal capacity. The law does not directly indicate the termination of the legal capacity of a citizen declared dead. The law is not talking about the "recognition of a citizen who deceased", but about the "declaration of his deceased", which emphasizes the difference between the establishment of the fact of death and the declaration of deceased, which does not exclude the possibility of the appearance of the person. Another thing is when there is a sufficient reason to believe that a citizen is alive, but is deliberately hidden. However, at the same time, the condition for the expiration of the deadlines established by the law is possible to declare it, except when such an announcement may affect criminal prosecution.

For the announcement of a citizen, the dead does not necessarily be preliminarily recognized as missing. According to Article 36 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan for declaring a citizen, it is necessary that at the place of his residence there were no information about its location within 3 years, and if he disappeared under the circumstances threatened with death or giving reason to assume its death from a certain accident - For six months. Therefore, after these

deadlines, interested persons are entitled to ask for a citizen's announcement to the dead, although no one has previously applied to recognizing him as missing. The announcement of a citizen who deceased also does not affect its legal capacity and capacity, if in fact this citizen is alive. Therefore, if a citizen is actually alive, he cannot be considered invalid legal capacity on the grounds that there is a court decision that declared him dead. The cancellation of the decision is not necessary for the restoration of legal capacity, but to restore those subjective civil and other rights, which were considered terminated in connection with the declaration of his deceased if the law allows them to restore. If a citizen was considered in this case by raising legal capacity, he would be deprived of the opportunity to apply to the court demanding the abolition of the court decision, which declared him dead.

Civil legal capacity is the overall ability to be a carrier of civil rights and duties envisaged and not provided for by law. Based on Art. 8 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, where it is written that civil rights and obligations arise from the grounds stipulated by law, as well as from the actions of citizens and legal entities, which, although not provided for by it, but by the general principle and the meaning of civil law generate civil rights and duties [1]. From this we can conclude that if the law does not provide any rights and obligations, this does not mean that a citizen cannot have them, the main thing that these rights and duties do not contradict the law.

The legal capacity of an individual is a prerequisite for the prevalence of concrete subjective rights (the right of private

property, the right to use the residential premises, the author's right to the literary work created by them). Subjective rights from a citizen arise in the presence of certain legal facts - actions and events on the basis of legal capacity (Article 8 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan). All legal facts (foundations) of the Republic of Uzbekistan envisaged by Article 8 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which generate civil rights and obligations can be divided into the following two main types: actions of individuals and legal entities, and events. The actions of individuals and legal entities are divided into: actions are legitimate and the actions of illegal. Legitimate actions, in turn, is divided into: the actions provided for by law and the actions of them not provided for, but such generating civil rights and obligations.

As a premise of copyright, the legal capacity itself is a special subjective law defended by the state against anyone who encroaches this right, in particular, impedes a citizen to implement its legal capacity, on the basis of Article 23 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan in accordance with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan proclaims equal legal capacity regardless of origin, gender, nationality, race, education, classes, social and property, relations to religion and other circumstances. The violation of the legal capacity equal to all individuals is prohibited by law - entails the invalidity of actions that violate such equality, in particularly dangerous cases - criminal offense.

Equality in the ability to be a carrier of civil rights and obligations does not mean, however, equality in specific subjective

rights. As long as there is a distribution by labor and material interest in labor results, differences in the specific volume of property rights of citizens remain. In addition, it is not necessary that every citizen has all subjective rights, the ability (ability) of possession of which is allowed by law, the content of the legal capacity of an individual. Not necessarily, for example, that every citizen becomes the author of a literary work.

Civil legal capacity is inseparable from the very existence of a person, it does not depend on its age, the state of health, from being able or not able to acquire rights [10].

Article 18 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan reveals the concept of the content of the legal capacity of citizens, provides that "citizens in accordance with the law may have property on the right of ownership"; inherit and call property; have savings in a bank; engage in entrepreneurship, dehqan (farmer) economy; another, not prohibited by law, activities; use hiring work; create legal entities; make transactions and participate in obligations; require compensation for harm; elective classes and place of residence; have the authorities of the author, science, literature, arts, images and other laws protected by law of intellectual activity; Other property and personal non-property rights [1].

This article does not contain an exhaustive transfer of all possible civil rights, whose subject can become a citizen. The law lists only the most important civil rights, such as the right of private property, the right to the results of scientific, technical and artistic creativity and others. Exhaustive transfer of all possible civil rights would not only be impractical, and it is

impossible, since the difference from other industries of law (for example, family) civil legislation does not contain a closed circle of possible civil law relations. Defining the content of civil legal capacity, Article 18 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, along with civil rights in the proper sense of the word, that is, the rights that are governed by civil law mentions and such a right of citizens as the right to "choose the genus of classes and place of residence" [1]. This right of citizens is fully secured by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, is not an object of civil law regulation in the exact sense. The procedure for election of the place of residence is determined by the norms of administrative legislation, and the protection of this right is carried out, as a rule, not in court, but in administrative procedure. Election of classes is mainly governed by labor law norms; Civil law norms in this area are valid only in order of exception (classes of individual creative or labor activities). It seems that such an expanded concept, "civil legal capacity" has been preserved in the current traditional legislation, since these rights were mentioned in the previously existing civil codexes [2].

In Article 18 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a list of the most significant civil rights, the subject of which can be a citizen. This article is complemented by new items, such as "to create legal entities, to be used by hired labor, to make transactions to participate in obligations." In accordance with the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the legal capacity of citizens is expanded.

According to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the use of citizens, there may be: plots of land

provided by the state to citizens to maintain utility farms, gardening and gardening, and such for individual housing construction. The content of the legal capacity of citizens includes not only the right to use these sites, but also the right to dispose of products manufactured by their products (their sale) and the right to receive relevant income.

Also in the list of rights contained in Article 18 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan contains new rights. Such, for example, how to occupy entrepreneurship (dekhkan) farming and other, not prohibited by law, activities. Although this can be considered a new half because in the previously current Civil Code of the Uzbek SSR, citizens were allowed to engage in hand-craft fishery, under which the activities of a citizen without the use of hired labor on the manufacture of products for the sale of the population or to provide paid household services. In the now the current Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, citizens are allowed not only to use hired labor, but also to create legal entities (private firms, small enterprises and others). Previously, the current Constitution of the Uzbek SSR admitted individual labor activities in the field of handicraft and crafts, agriculture, domestic service of the population, as well as other work activities based exclusively on the personal labor of citizens and their family members.

Article 18 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan shall indicate such rights that are not related to civil law - this is the right to choose classes and place of residence. These are broader rights considered by the constitutional and partly labor and administrative legislation. The use of a citizen of these rights is an important

prerequisite for the realization of them of civil legal capacity than, apparently, it is explained by the indication of them in Article 18 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The purpose of direct indication in the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan of civil rights and obligations is the desire to legally consolidate the most important rights and obligations from the point of view, to make this norm more clearly and affordable. List all rights that may have citizens are impossible and appropriate, since relations regulated by civil law are constantly developing, new ones. Therefore, listed rights, in Article 18 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the content of civil legal capacity is not exhausted. A citizen can belong to other property and personal non-property rights, the only condition, to these rights is that they do not contradict the general principles of civil law and would not be prohibited by law.

The content of the legal capacity of citizens includes the ability to have duties. Citizens can participate in obligations, acting as a debtor, obliged to make a certain action in favor of another [1]: somehow pass the property, perform work, to provide services, pay money, or abstain from a certain action, and the lender has the right to demand from Debtor fulfillment of his duties.

In the property relations and the results of intellectual activity, the owner's right corresponds to the duty of any citizen not to violate this right. No one can infringe the honor and dignity of a citizen, his business reputation.

V. Slope

With a sufficient settlement of civil legal capacity in the Civil Code of the Republic of

Uzbekistan and other regulatory documents, it is nevertheless to formulate some proposals for improving civil legislation in the field of civil legal and legal capacity.

First, in Article 17 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, legal capacity is defined as the ability to have civil rights and obligations. Article 18 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan gives a list of civil rights. In this regard, the question arises about the lists of the duties that are also the content of legal capacity. If there is no question of their responsibilities in relation to those who have reached 14 years old, then the child has a question about their civil obligations against children from the moment of birth and achieve a certain age (for example, 14 years). Therefore, in our opinion, in the concept of the legal capacity of citizens in civil law (Article 17 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan) should be determined only rights, and not obligations, since the young due to its age and psychological factors cannot have civil obligations. Currently, in Article 17 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to bring a specific list of civil duties belonging to the concept of civil legal capacity.

Secondly, in Article 17 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is indicated that a citizen is emphasized from the moment of birth to the very death. Determining the moments of birth and death is not subject to legal science, since it

is a purely physiological concepts. For the right, it is only important for the right that from the moment the citizen is considered born (medicine, as a rule, is guided in this case the criterion for the beginning of independent respiration), the child acquires civil legal capacity. The law is referred to as one of the possible heirs of the child, which is conceived during the life of the testator, but born alive after his death, i.e. Not yet born child (Article 1118 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan). Such a child is not empowered or some subjective rights, but the law provides for the protection of his interests as a possible heir, which comes down to the consolidation of its possible share in the inheritance, provided that the child is born alive. If the child is born dead, he will not be designed to inherit. Therefore, in our opinion, it should be provided in civil law (Art. 17 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan) in some cases the possibility of civil legal capacity before the birth of a child, i.e. A child who is in the mother's womb from 6 to 9 months. If this provision is enshrined in the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, this will lead to a logical compliance with such civil contracts as donation, inheritance in the will. Since at present, when concluding this type of civil law transactions, there are cases of the names by the heirs and belonging persons who have not yet been born. But they are not subjects of civil law and their legal capacity, respectively, is not provided for by the Civil Code.

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